

CAUSES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL BURNOUT AMONG STUDENTS DANCERS: A BASIS FOR PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES

Jazmhine D. Mercado, Baby Jean E. Mendoza, Xander A. De Torres LPT

*School of Teacher Education, CSTC College of Sciences, Technology and Communications Inc.,
Sariaya, Quezon, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18113355>

ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers and to propose preventive strategies. Age, sex, and level of psychological burnout, along with the causes of psychological burnout in terms of high-intensity training, lack of rest and recovery, academic pressure, and social expectations, were determined. The research surveyed student dancers from a private institution in Sariaya, Quezon, using a total population sampling. A descriptive correlational method with a quantitative approach was employed, and the data were collected using a self-made and adapted printed questionnaire. Statistical tools utilized for analysis included Frequency, Percentage Distribution, and Summation to describe the sample, Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM) to determine the level of different burnout causes, and the Kruskal-Wallis test to determine if there were significant differences in the causes of burnout across the different student dancer profiles. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of the respondents are aged 12-15 and has a large number of female. Furthermore, it is revealed that the highest causes of psychological burnout are academic pressure with a WAM of 2.92, and lack of rest and recovery are the lowest, with 2.4 psychological burnout among the student dancers surveyed. Statistical analysis indicated that there were no significant differences in the causes of psychological burnout of the respondents when grouped according to their profile. Based on these findings, the researchers proposed a preventive strategy aimed at lessening the experience of psychological burnout among student dancers.

Keywords: *Preventive strategies, Psychological burnout, Student dancers*

INTRODUCTION

Dance is an essential part of the Philippine educational system as stated in DepEd Order No. 21, s. 2019, which outlines the Policy Guidelines on the K-12 Basic Education Program, dance is a key component of the Philippine educational system. Within the Physical Education (PE) curriculum, dance is valued for its benefits to cultural awareness, physical health, and self-expression. The importance of movement-based activities, such as dance, in promoting holistic development, fostering lifelong well-being, and encouraging creative expression is highlighted by the order. Similarly, CHED Memorandum Order No. 39, s. 2021 describes the structure for PE programs in higher education institutions, incorporating dance as a crucial instructional element that improves students' learning and general health.

Student dancers are individuals who choose to commit to dance and performing while pursuing their academic studies at the institution. Most of them are members of the official dance troupe of the institution they are in, and they joined through auditions. These students perform when there is an event at the institution, and they just do not perform inside; they also represent the school in competitions outside the campus, carrying the name and pride of both their troupe and institution.

Due to their willingness and determination, student dancers experience habits that lead to psychological burnout. According to the study by Blevins et al. (2019), it is stated here that they need to recover from the stress and physical demands of training. On the other hand, if not able to recover properly, they develop maladaptive behavioral responses where they feel exhaustion, discomfort, and physical strain can all lead to negative training outcomes, including burnout and overexertion. Spinner (2022) has a term called a mastery trap, where pressure from perfection delays growth. Pressuring oneself to constantly improve, the “I have to get better” mindset. The pursuit of perfection, even if overworked, affects both physical and mental health and negatively impacts the quality of training and performance as well.

Psychological burnout is a condition of physical, mental, and emotional exhaustion caused by the inability to cope with persistent stress (Taylor, 2015). It is often triggered by extended periods in an unfavorable social environment, stressful mental states, and an existential crisis caused by a mismatch of ideological values, expectations, and reality (Morozov & Sadokha, 2023).

Student dancers balance rigorous dance schedules with academic coursework can lead to stress and fatigue, as dancers often have overbooked schedules that leave little time for rest (Jowett & Cockerill, 2018). In alignment with this, in a recent article in the *Knight Krier*, the pressures of remembering routines, maintaining technique, and striving for improvement in dance, combined with the increasing demands of schoolwork, create a stressful environment for many student dancers. This delicate balance often leads to exhaustion and mental strain, with dancers reporting forgotten homework

assignments and an overwhelming sense of having too little time to succeed in both their artistic and academic pursuits (Ballas, 2023).

While existing literature explores academic stress and performance pressure faced by student-athletes and performers, there is limited research specifically addressing the causes of psychological burnout faced by student dancers at the institution. Given this, the researchers decided to determine the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers. The findings can help researchers develop preventive strategies to manage and reduce burnout, as well as provide insights for dance coaches and educators in creating more supportive environments for student dancers. The study took place among the student dancers in one of the secondary private institutions in Sariaya, Quezon.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers as a basis for preventive strategies.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents, in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex; and
 - 1.3 Level of Psychological Burnout?
2. What are the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers, in terms of:
 - 2.1 High Intensity Training;
 - 2.2 Lack of Rest and Recovery;
 - 2.3 Academic Pressure; and
 - 2.4 Social Expectations?
3. Is there a significant difference in the causes of psychological burnout of the respondents when they are grouped according to their profile?
4. What preventive strategies can be made based on the results of the study to help lessen the psychological burnout of student dancers?

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference in the causes of psychological burnout of the respondents when they are grouped according to their profile.

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

The study was conducted in one of the private institutions in Sariaya, Quezon, which offers secondary and tertiary programs. The institution supports a Dance Troupe

that gives the students a chance to perform and join competitions while managing their academic responsibilities. Based on informal interviews with student dancers, it was revealed that they have participated in various competitions, including events organized by the Department of Education (DepEd), the Provincial Government, United Private Educational Institutions of Quezon (UPEIQ), and the National Alliance of Private Schools Philippines Inc. (NAPSPHIL). Additionally, these student dancers frequently perform intermission numbers at school-wide events, further increasing their dance commitments.

Despite their achievements, informal interviews also highlighted the struggles student dancers face in balancing academics and dance. Many reported feelings of burnout and exhaustion, with many of them even thinking about quitting due to overwhelming responsibilities from both commitments.

Therefore, the study determined the specific causes of psychological burnout among the student dancers and analyzed its impact on their well-being and academic performance. By gaining a deeper understanding of the struggles student dancers faced, this research provided insights into the challenges they experienced when navigating their academic responsibilities alongside the demands of their commitment to dance.

Research Population and Sample

The respondents of this study were student dancers in a private institution who were enrolled in the academic year 2024-2025. The researchers focused on student dancers as they have firsthand experience balancing academic responsibilities and dance commitments, making them suitable respondents for the study. Based on the gathered baseline data, the locale has a total of 51 enrolled student dancers from different levels: 23 from the junior high school, 14 from senior high school, and 14 in college, respectively.

The researchers employed the total population sampling, selecting all 51 student dancers. Since the entire population of student dancers is included, the study ensures a comprehensive understanding of their experiences regarding psychological burnout. The researchers coordinated with school administrators and Culture and Arts Coordinator to set the schedule for data gathering.

The study used total population sampling, where the research population, or target population, refers to the entire group of individuals, objects, or events that share specific characteristics relevant to the study (Thomas, 2022). The selected respondents were the student dancers in the said institution.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers followed several steps in gathering the needed data for the study. After the research instrument was examined and validated, the researchers sought permission to collect the needed data. The researchers assured the respondents that the data gathered would only be used for the sake of the study and not leaked anywhere, which was attached in a printed questionnaire that was distributed to the student dancers. After the given time, the researcher collects the answered questionnaires. After gathering

the data, it was subjected to presentation, interpretation, and analysis of the collected data. Furthermore, the data were computed using various statistical treatments.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire was divided into two sections: demographic profile and causes of psychological burnout. The demographic profile included the age, sex, and level of psychological burnout of the respondents. The causes section determined factors such as high training intensity, lack of rest and recovery, academic pressure, and social expectations. Additionally, the section measuring the level of psychological burnout, which is a sub-variable under the profile of the respondents, was adapted from Section A of the questionnaire used in the study by Tununu and Martin (2020) titled "Prevalence of burnout among nurses working at a psychiatric hospital in the Western Cape." Only six of the seven statements were used in this study. The researchers obtained approval from the research adviser before working with professional validators. Internal validator, external validator, and language editor reviewed the research instrument. Responses to the reviews were applied to modify the questionnaire.

The questionnaire consisted of checklists in survey form, which included a 4-point scale, and the respondents could answer like "SA" for Strongly Agree, "A" for Agree, "DA" for Disagree, and "SD" for Strongly Disagree to the causes of psychological burnout. The adapted questionnaire used a 6-point scale, with respondents going from "6" Every Day, down to "0" Never.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The researchers used the following statistical treatment to analyze, present, and interpret the data gathered precisely.

For the demographic profile, such as age, sex, and level of psychological burnout, percentage and frequency distribution were utilized. The formula is shown below:

Formula

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

$\%$ = *percentage*

f = *frequency or number of cases in any categories*

N = *total number of cases in all categories*

Additionally, for the level of psychological burnout specifically, summation was used in determining the overall level of psychological burnout. The Formula is shown below:

Formula

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$$

Where:

i = index of the summation

n = upper limit of summation

The level of psychological burnout was computed using an adapted 6-Point scale as shown below:

Point Scale	Descriptive Analysis
0	Never
1	A Few Times Per Year
2	Once a Month
3	A Few Times Per Week
4	Once a Week
5	A Few Times Per Week
6	Every Day

Based on the total score of 6-point scale, the following interpretations are applied:

- Total 17 or less: Low-level burnout
- Total between 18 and 29 inclusive: Moderate burnout
- Total over 30: High-level burnout

For the causes of psychological burnout, such as high training intensity, lack of rest and recovery, academic pressure, and social expectations, the researchers utilized the Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM). The formula is shown below:

Formula:

$$W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i X_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i}$$

Where:

W = *Weighted Mean*

n = *number of terms to be averaged*

W_i = *weights applied to x values*

X_i = *data values to be averaged*

The researchers used a 4-Point Scale, and interpreted the result using the continuous scale below:

Point Scale	Mean Ranges	Verbal Interpretation
4	3.26 - 4.00	Strongly Agree (SA)
3	2.51 - 3.25	Agree (A)
2	1.76 - 2.50	Disagree (D)
1	1.00 - 1.75	Strongly Disagree (SD)

For the significant difference in the causes of psychological burnout of the respondents when they are grouped according to their profile, researchers used the Kruskal-Wallis test. The formula is shown below:

Formula:

$$H = \frac{12}{N(N+1)} \left(\frac{R_1^2}{n_1} + \frac{R_2^2}{n_2} + \dots + \frac{R_k^2}{n_k} \right) - 3(N+1)$$

Where:

k = *the number of samples,*

n_i = *size of the i th sample,*

N = *sum of the sample sizes, and*

R_i = *sum of the ranks of the i th sample*

Scope and Limitations

This study focused on determining the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers as a basis for creating preventive strategies among student dancers. The variables considered in the study consist of the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, and level of psychological burnout, and causes of psychological burnout in terms of high-intensity training, lack of rest and recovery, academic pressure, and social expectations.

Data were collected from one of the private institutions located in Sariaya, Quezon. The respondents in this research were the 51 student dancers from junior and senior high school, and college level, enrolled for the school year 2024-2025. The researchers utilized a descriptive survey method in a quantitative approach for the research design and used a total population sampling technique to identify the respondents. Self-made and adapted printed questionnaires were used, incorporating a 4-point Likert and a 6-point Likert questionnaire scale. Through quantitative means, the researchers have numerical insights about the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers. The Frequency, Percentage Distribution, Summation, Weighted Arithmetic Mean (WAM), and Kruskal-Wallis test were used to interpret the data.

However, the researchers encountered some limitations during this study. These included the availability of the respondents and the limited timeframe given to the researchers, which was only one week. To address the issue of availability, the researchers surveyed during the free time of the respondents. As for the timeframe, it is resolved by having appropriate time management at the end of the research.

RESULTS

The following are the areas of investigation that were considered in this study: (1) profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and level of psychological burnout; (2) causes of psychological burnout in terms of high training intensity, lack of rest and recovery, academic pressure, and social expectations; and (3) whether there is a significant difference in the causes of psychological burnout of the respondents when they are grouped according to the profile. These data are analyzed through frequency and percentage distribution, summation, weighted arithmetic mean, and the Kruskal-Wallis test. The data was presented in a table format.

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Profile of the respondents in terms of Age

Descriptor	Frequency	Percentage
12 - 15 years old	23	45
16 - 17 years old	14	27
18 years old and above	14	27
Total	51	100

Table 2. Profile of the respondents in terms of Sex

Descriptor	Frequency	Percentage
Female	38	75
Male	13	25

Total	51	100
-------	----	-----

Table 3. Profile of the respondents in terms of Level of Psychological Burnout

Descriptor	Frequency	Percentage
Low-level Burnout	30	59
Moderate Burnout	16	31
High-level Burnout	5	10
Total	51	100

Scale	Descriptive Analysis
0	Never
1	A Few Times Per Year
2	Once a Month
3	A Few Times Per Month
4	Once a Week
5	A Few Times Per Week
6	Every Day

Part II. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers

Table 4. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms High Intensity Training

Code	Descriptor	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
10	After a long day of practice, the mind and body just want to shut down, avoiding social interactions or additional responsibilities.	3.12	Agree
3	The risk of collapsing during training feels real, but the thought focuses on pushing through than addressing it.	2.98	Agree
1	The intense physical demands of training makes it difficult to recover, leading to constant exhaustion and mental fatigue.	2.92	Agree
5	Extreme fatigue causes muscles to tighten, reducing flexibility, affecting performance.	2.88	Agree
4	After training session, the body feels numb or unresponsive after intense training sessions, making basic movements difficult.	2.86	Agree
9	The training sometimes make muscles too tight, limiting flexibility needed for certain dance styles.	2.71	Agree
6	The pressure to keep up with demanding routines causes anxiety and stress, leading to questions about the commitment to dance.	2.63	Agree
2	Due to extreme fatigue, the ability to continue in training and dance becomes a question.	2.53	Agree
7	The exhaustion is so severe that there is a sense of hopelessness about continuing with dance.	2.49	Disagree
8	High-intensity exercise causes physical pain and discomfort, which leads to frustration and negative emotions.	2.47	Disagree
Average WAM		2.72	Agree

Note. The WAM which stands for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, and 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 5. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of Lack of Rest and Recovery

Code	Descriptor	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
2	Sleep feels like a luxury as it is often sacrificed for training, leading to exhaustion and constant headaches.	3.06	Agree
9	Personal time and social activities are sacrificed because every free moment is dedicated to training	2.92	Agree
7	There is pressure to perform at peak levels, even when the body signals the need for rest.	2.86	Agree
8	The guilt of resting feels heavier than the exhaustion itself due to peers being dedicated.	2.86	Agree
10	Pain has become a normal part of training, making it hard to recognize when the body needs rest leading to insufficient rest and recovery	2.84	Agree
5	No time to rest as school, training, and life all demand attention, leaving little room for recovery	2.82	Agree
6	Injuries are ignored or downplayed to avoid missing training or practice	2.57	Agree
4	Lack of sleep forces dependence on caffeine to stay awake, yet exhaustion makes it impossible to focus on schoolwork.	2.31	Disagree
1	The body is permanently sore, and there's no time to heal.	2.18	Disagree
3	There is no longer any excitement to dance, only fatigue from lack of proper rest	1.63	Strongly Disagree
Average WAM		2.61	Agree

Note. The WAM which stands for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, and 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 6. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of Academic Pressure

No.	Descriptor	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
1	There is pressure to maintain high grades while balancing school and dance.	3.29	Strongly Agree
4	The fear of academic failure causes anxiety.	3.25	Strongly Agree
6	The expectation to be perfect in both academics and dance creates stress.	3.02	Agree
5	The pressure to succeed academically negatively impacts mental health.	3.00	Agree
7	Stress from upcoming academic deadlines and dance competitions is common.	2.98	Agree
10	The volume of schoolwork and rehearsals causes feelings of being overwhelmed.	2.88	Agree
9	Pressure from school leads to sacrificing sleep or rest.	2.84	Agree
2	The expectation to meet academic goals set by parents causes stress.	2.75	Agree
3	There is frequent comparison of academic performance with that of classmates.	2.73	Agree
8	Focusing on schoolwork is difficult due to dance commitments.	2.47	Disagree
Average WAM		2.92	Agree

Note. The WAM which stands for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, and 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Table 7. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of Social Expectations

Code	Descriptor	WAM	Verbal Interpretation
9	Feedback from coach or coaches influences perceptions of worth as a dancer.	3.53	Strongly Agree
10	There is pressure to meet the expectations of coaches or mentors, regardless of personal circumstances.	3.25	Strongly Agree
1	There is pressure to maintain a certain body image to fit into the dance community.	3.06	Agree
8	The family often expects that since dance is a choice, all other responsibilities should be handled as well, leading to added pressure and burnout.	3.00	Agree
6	Anxiety about judgment from peers regarding academic and dance achievements is common.	2.78	Agree
7	Social media influences my perception of what a "perfect" dancer should look like.	2.75	Agree
2	Peer judgment regarding academic and dance performance is a concern.	2.73	Agree
4	Social media creates unrealistic expectations regarding appearance and performance in dance.	2.61	Agree
5	Comparing oneself to others in the dance community leads to feelings of inadequacy.	2.55	Agree
3	The need to fit in with the dance group adds stress.	2.39	Disagree
Average WAM		2.87	Agree

Note. The WAM which stands for weighted arithmetic mean was used to interpret the survey responses. In this context, the range of 1.00 - 1.74 indicates Strongly Disagree the range of 1.75 - 2.49 indicates Disagree, the range of 2.50 - 3.24 indicates Agree, and 3.25 - 4.00 indicates Strongly Agree.

Part III. Difference in the Causes of Psychological Burnout of the respondents when Grouped According to their Profile

Table 8. Difference in the Causes of Psychological Burnout of the respondents when Grouped According to their Profile

Group	Variable	H statistic	p value	Statistical Decision	Interpretation
Age	High Intensity Training	2.740	.254	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Lack of Rest and Recovery	3.409	.182	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Academic Pressure	3.742	.154	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Social Expectations	4.093	.129	Accept H_o	Not Significant
Sex	High Intensity Training	.136	.712	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Lack of Rest and Recovery	.682	.409	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Academic Pressure	.004	.948	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Social Expectations	.482	.488	Accept H_o	Not Significant
Level of Psychological Burnout	High Intensity Training	.136	.712	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Lack of Rest and Recovery	.682	.409	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Academic Pressure	.004	.948	Accept H_o	Not Significant
	Social Expectations	.482	.488	Accept H_o	Not Significant

Note. There are 23 respondents whose ages range 12 - 15 years old, 14 whose ages range 16 - 17 years old and 14 whose ages range 18 years old and above. By sex, there are 38 respondents who are female, and 13 male respondents. Based on level of psychological burnout, 30 respondents are classified as low-level burnout, 16 who are moderate burnout, and 5 who are high-level burnout. Differences were analyzed at 0.05 alpha level.

DISCUSSION

Part I. Profile of the Respondents

Profile of the respondents in terms of **Age**

Table 1 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age. The “12-15 years old” has the highest frequency with 23 respondents (45%). At the same time, “16-17 years old” and “18 years old and above” showed the same frequencies with 14 respondents (27%) each.

The results reveal that the majority of participants fall within the 12-15 age range, suggesting this group may be more exposed to or affected by factors contributing to psychological burnout. This highlights the need in prioritizing the early intervention of the preventive strategies that is designed to meet on their developmental stage as they may lack the coping mechanisms in handling both commitments, the academic and extracurricular stress. Meanwhile, the equal representation of the 16–17 and 18+ age groups provides an opportunity for meaningful comparison across age brackets, which can help determine if burnout levels increase, decrease, or change in nature as students grow older. Overall, the age distribution implies that while younger students require focused support, burnout is a concern across all age groups and must be addressed through age-appropriate programs and policies.

The findings of Luga et al. (2023) emphasized the prevalence of burnout among students, highlighting that among a large sample of Slovenian adolescents between the ages of 15 and 19, 6.7% of them had a high level of burnout. In the meantime, research conducted on a sample of French students revealed that more than 40% of them displayed symptoms of burnout that were comparable to those seen in professional settings, highlighting how students are psychologically exhausted, which suggests the need for further research and treatments.

Profile of the respondents in terms of **Sex**

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of sex. The female category has the highest frequency with 38 respondents (75%). While male category has 13 frequencies with 13 respondents (25%).

The data indicates a significantly higher number of female student dancers compared to males in the study population. The findings show a significant sex gap among student dancers, where the population is more female. This distribution shows that while male representation is still far lower, female students make up the majority of the dance student body at the school under study. The results unequivocally demonstrate that there are significantly more female student dancers in this sample than males.

Lopez (2017), citing Hagood (2007), states that biases toward dancers and dance courses may reduce the number of students who choose this profession. It is not easy for male dancers to handle how society treats masculinity in the field of dancing. Analysis of

posture, movement and body image by many male dance students can shape their self-confidence and experience in dance.

Profile of the respondents in terms of **Level of Psychological Burnout**

Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of level of psychological burnout. The Low-level Burnout category has the highest frequency with 30 respondents (59%). While High-level Burnout categories have lower frequencies with 5 respondents (10%).

The data reveals distinct patterns in psychological burnout levels among the 51 surveyed student dancers. Thirty respondents, representing 59% of the sample, reported experiencing low-level burnout. A significant portion, consisting of 16 dancers or 31% of the total, indicated moderate burnout levels. Additionally, 5 participants, accounting for 10% of the group, exhibited high-level burnout symptoms.

These figures demonstrate that while the majority of student dancers manage to maintain low burnout levels, a considerable combined percentage (41%) of the population experiences either moderate or high degrees of psychological burnout. The distribution highlights the varying stress experiences within the student dancer population, with a notable minority reporting substantial burnout symptoms.

According to Yang (2004), as mentioned in Rahmati (2015), it is a state brought on by academic rigor, a heavy course load, or a number of various psychological factors. It is distinguished by its emotional exhaustion, wherein students feel a severe depletion of their emotional resources. This extreme fatigue is considered a fundamental psychological element of the burnout syndrome.

Part II. Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers

Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms **High Intensity Training**

Table 4 shows the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers in terms of High-Intensity Training. It has an overall weighted arithmetic mean of 2.72, with verbal interpretation of agree, meaning students considered High-Intensity Training a cause of psychological burnout. The statement, "*After a long day of practice, the mind and body just want to shut down, avoiding social interactions or additional responsibilities.*", got the highest WAM of 3.12, with the verbal interpretation of agree. On the other hand, the statement "*High-intensity exercise causes physical pain and discomfort, which leads to frustration and negative emotions*", with lowest WAM of 2.47, with the verbal interpretation of disagree.

The data indicates that high-intensity training is a significant factor to psychological burnout among student dancers, who face severe physical and mental fatigue following demanding practice sessions. Numerous dancers find themselves retreating from social engagements and shunning extra responsibilities due to the immense tiredness brought on by intense training. While the drive to persevere through challenging routines adds to

their stress, the frustration due to physical discomfort seems to be a lesser priority, implying that dancers are more concerned with endurance and performance than with the strain they experience. These insights highlight the necessity of integrating adequate recovery times to maintain both physical health and mental well-being in the future.

The findings align with the study of Smith et al. (2024) examines fatigue and recovery from the perspective of South African ballet dancers. Tiredness is usually ignored by participants as they appeared to be very motivated and driven on their chosen career, admitting that their behaviors trigger injuries and unhealthy effects on their careers. Motivated behaviors, high external pressure, and the expectations of the audience and the management were named as contributing factors to fatigue from the study. Similarly, Reynolds (2024) noted that emotional stress and exhaustion affect coordination and increase the risk of injury, while Daychak (2025) indicates that one of the causes of burnout is overtraining. Understanding how overtraining is vital, as it may result in harmful effects. It is also illustrated under the Intense Training Schedules that rigorous daily training sessions, repetitive physical demands, and lack of adequate rest and recovery time are one among the causes of psychological burnout.

Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of ***Lack of Rest and Recovery***

Table 5 presents the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers in terms of Lack of Rest and Recovery. It has an overall weighted arithmetic mean of 2.61, with verbal interpretation of agree, meaning students considered Lack of Rest and Recovery a cause of psychological burnout. The statement, "*Sleep feels like a luxury as it is often sacrificed for training, leading to exhaustion and constant headaches,*" got the highest WAM of 3.06, with the verbal interpretation of agree. On the other hand, the statement "*There is no longer any excitement to dance, only fatigue from lack of proper rest*" lowest WAM of 1.63, with the verbal interpretation of strongly disagree.

The data explicitly shows that student dancers recognized sleep deprivation and pressure as significant causes of psychological burnout. Nevertheless, they strongly disagree that they have lost their passion for dance. This contradiction suggests that despite the exhaustion, their dedication to commit to their craft and chosen extracurricular activities drives them to keep going, often at the expense of their well-being. This highlights how symptoms are overlooked when strong passion and dedication persist.

The findings were supported by previous literature. Sleep has consistently been recognized by athletes, both elite and sub-elite, as the most vital recovery technique (Tuomilehto et al., 2016). In addition, as stated by Saqib et al. (2018), when students participating in extracurricular activities are over-scheduled, they may try to go beyond what they can offer in extracurricular activities to show their exceptional performance, which can result in some serious injuries. And if they are over-scheduled, they need to rest much more to fully recover from the fatigue and exhaustion. And this can result in students feeling exhausted and losing motivation, making them less interested in participating. Over-scheduled demands more rest for full recovery.

Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of **Academic Pressure**

Table 6 presents the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers in terms of Academic Pressure. It has an overall weighted arithmetic mean of 2.92, with verbal interpretation of agree, meaning students considered Academic Pressure a cause of psychological burnout. The statement, "*There is pressure to maintain high grades while balancing school and dance.*", has the highest WAM of 3.29, with the verbal interpretation of agree. On the other hand, the statement "*Focusing on schoolwork is difficult due to dance commitments*" got the lowest WAM of 2.47, with the verbal interpretation of strongly disagree.

The data revealed that student dancers acknowledge academic pressure as a major contributor to psychological burnout, yet they do not strongly agree that dance commitments hinder their focus on schoolwork. This contradiction suggests that while academic challenges and stress impact their mental well-being, their ability to balance responsibilities remains intact despite the pressure. It highlights how student dancers perceive the struggle of maintaining high grades and rigorous training as demanding but manageable, driven by their dedication to both academics and their chosen extracurricular activity.

The findings align with the study of Bernal et al. (2024) that investigates the effect of pressure in school and lifestyle habits on Filipino university students. The research points out that a lot of student stress comes from the pressure to meet academic requirements, since managing studies and personal health becomes very difficult for them. Strict expectations for themselves become one of the main reasons that students feel so much stress and worry.

A large workload, similar to stress, makes it difficult for students to keep up with their college work. In addition, disappointment in grades and low confidence lead to academic fear and eventually lessen students' interest in studying in class. The pressure to succeed in future work and please parents tends to stress students out, with little contribution from competitive friends. The authors note that students are strong with water intake, but at the same time, rely on caffeinated drinks to help them manage their emotions. Not sleeping enough and exercising less are common issues, and students commonly eat poorly when they are under high stress.

Causes of Psychological Burnout among Student Dancers in terms of **Social Expectations**

Table 7 presents the causes of psychological burnout among student dancers in terms of Social Expectations. It has an overall weighted arithmetic mean of 2.87, with verbal interpretation of agree, meaning students considered Social Expectations a cause of psychological burnout. The statement, "*Feedback from coach or coaches influences perceptions of worth as a dancer.*", got the highest WAM of 3.53, with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The statement "*The need to fit in with the dance group adds stress.*", lowest WAM of 2.39, with the verbal interpretation of disagree.

The data explicitly indicates that the feedback dancers receive from coaches strongly impacts their self-perception, potentially increasing anxiety and stress. On the other side, fitting in with peers may cause some stress, but it is not as significant a factor as other social expectations. This suggests that student dancers were more affected by performance-related pressures rather than being socially accepted within the dance community, even though external validation and high expectations add to stress.

The findings align with the study of Brunner (2024) investigated the psychological impacts of competitive dance on young dancers. The research highlighted that while competitive dance can foster self-confidence and resilience, it also introduces psychological challenges such as anxiety and stress. These challenges are often amplified by coaches' expectations and peer competition, underscoring the significant influence of social expectations on dancers' mental health.

Part III. Difference in the Causes of Psychological Burnout of the respondents when Grouped According to their Profile

Table 8 demonstrates the differences in the perception of causes of psychological burnout based on age, sex, and the level of psychological burnout found significant in the Kruskal-Wallis test.

Starting with age, High-Intensity Training had an H statistic of 2.740 and a p-value of .254; Lack of Rest and Recovery was .182 with a H value of 3.409; Academic Pressure was .154 at an H value of 3.742; and lastly, Social Expectations showed an H value of 4.093 with .129 as the p-value. For sex, results were High-Intensity Training (.136, $p = .712$), Lack of Rest and Recovery (.682, $p = .409$), Academic Pressure (.004, $p = .948$), and Social Expectations (.482, $p = .488$). Thus, the same for the level of psychological burnout, High-Intensity Training (.136, $p = .712$), Lack of Rest and Recovery (.682, $p = .409$), Academic Pressure (.004, $p = .948$), and Social Expectations (.482, $p = .488$). Since all the p-values were above the considered alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted, indicating there were no significant differences in the perceived causes of burnout across all profile groups.

The data revealed that perceptions regarding the causes of psychological burnout are consistent across different age brackets, sexes, and burnout levels. Whether a student dancer is younger or older, male or female, or experiencing low to high levels of burnout, they tend to identify the same primary contributors, such as intense training demands, insufficient rest, academic load, and societal expectations, as key stressors. This uniformity implies that such challenges are not confined to specific demographic groups but are embedded within the broader student dancer experience. The consistent responses across profile variables underscore the systemic nature of these stressors, highlighting that psychological burnout arises from shared conditions within the dance environment rather than from individual differences.

Building upon these findings, Ramirez and Jakaub (2021), the association between age (mean = 32) and the burnout personal achievement dimension was investigated. According to the results, students in both the Master of Social Work (MSW) and Bachelor

of Social Work (BSW) programs exhibited moderately strong scores on the personal achievement scale. The statistical analysis showed a strong negative link ($r = -0.300$, $p < 0.001$) between age and academic burnout, implying that burnout rates among MSW and BSW students decrease as they get older. Moreover, Lopez (2017) learned that neither gender nor year level had a major impact on mental outcomes or dancers' preferences for dance styles. Supporting this, Olson et al. (2025) investigated stress, burnout, and study engagement among 947 university students, revealing no significant sex differences in burnout or study engagement.

Conclusions

The findings have led the researchers to the following conclusion. After analyzing the data, the current researchers arrived at the following conclusions:

1. Results revealed that most of the respondents are female student dancers aged between 12-15 years. Most of them rated their psychological burnout experience at a low level.
2. Among all the stressors, academic pressure from dance coaches emerged as the most prominent factor contributing to psychological burnout. Specifically, pressure in maintaining high grades while balancing school and dance. On the other hand, lack of rest and recovery served as the least common cause of psychological burnout among the respondents.
3. Age, sex, and level of burnout do not significantly affect how student dancers perceive these stressors, suggesting a shared experience of pressure and stress within the community regardless of background.
4. The findings led the researchers to develop preventive strategies in a PowToon animation. The video reiterates the results of the study. It discusses the activities for preventive strategies tailored and addressed to student dancers and dance coaches, which focuses on academic pressure, the primary factor of psychological burnout among student dancers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered based on the findings and conclusions obtained from the study.

1. Student dancers are encouraged to understand and gain a deeper understanding of the causes of psychological burnout. This in-depth knowledge served as the basis of their responsible selection of training, stress management techniques, and overall health, which will further their dance experience and academic pursuits, fulfilling.
2. Dance coaches are suggested to have insight into the psychological challenges student dancers are facing. By gaining a better understanding of these, dance coaches can develop less harmful and more supportive training environments. Additionally, they were able to employ innovative strategies to improve coach-athlete relationships and lower the

risk of psychological burnout in student dancers. This created an environment where student dancers could thrive and succeed more.

3. Teachers can benefit from the study by gaining a deeper understanding of the unique pressures that student dancers face in balancing academics and dance. With this insight, they were able to adjust academic expectations, provide mental health support, and design more flexible schedules. These efforts will support student-dancers' well-being and help improve their overall academic and artistic performance.

4. Future researchers are encouraged to further develop more targeted interventions for psychological burnout of student dancers, as well as inform best practices and support systems in the performing arts community, contributing to more effective research in the future.

Output of the Study

The primary outcome of the study was a set of preventive strategies aimed at helping student dancers reduce psychological burnout. These strategies were presented through a Powtoon animation titled "Keeping the Rhythm: Strategies to Prevent Psychological Burnout in Student Dancers." This animation addresses the principal issue found in the study: the challenge of academic pressure and stress associated with trying to maintain good grades while doing two commitments, school and dance as an extra-curricular activity. The material is tailored to present practical, creative, and strategies that are relatable and promote balance and student dancers' well-being.

The output showcased two categories of preventive strategies, one is addressed to student dancers and the one for dance coaches. The activities addressed to student dancers include Study & Stretch, Priority Planner Challenge, and lastly, Mind Dump Journaling. These preventive strategies are intended to improve focus, manage time, and release mental stress. Additionally, the preventive strategies activity to be suggested to dance coaches and are encouraged to implement Focus Flow Warm-Up, Academic Pulse Check, and Success Shoutouts that support student dancers academically and emotionally within the training environment. The approach of preventive strategies directly responds to the predominant factor contributing to psychological burnout among student dancers by promoting holistic support systems.

This digital resource functions as a sustainable, visual, and interactive instrument for student dancers and dance coaches. It serves to merge academic awareness with emotional well-being for dance students. Such an approach creates not only an atmosphere of care, thus making it alright for students to go after any mental health or physical condition challenges they may face, but also an environment in which performance improves.

I. Title

“Keeping the Rhythm: Strategies to Prevent Psychological Burnout in Student Dancers”

II. Objectives

At the end of the animation, viewers will be able to:

- Identify practical and creative preventive strategies to help lessen psychological burnout in student dancers.
- Recognize the importance of managing academic pressure alongside dance commitments.
- Identify the preventive strategies that dance coaches can use to help lessen psychological burnout in student dancers.
- Apply these strategies to promote balance, focus, and overall well-being within dance and academic environments.

III. Rationale

For this study, the primary outcome was a list of Preventive Strategies presented using PowToon animation aimed at helping student dancers lessen psychological burnout. The animation is made to tackle the key finding revealed by the research: There is pressure to maintain high grades while balancing school and dance. Using the results of the study and SOP4 as support, the animation was designed to assist student dancers and coaches in using helpful strategies to avoid psychological burnout.

There are two kinds of strategies the animation suggests, one for dancers and another for their coaches. Start with the Priority Planner Challenge, then improve your concentration by Study and Stretch and finally use Mind Dump Journaling to unwind your mind. Dance coaches should plan the Focus Flow Warm-Up, Academic Pulse Check and Success Shoutouts, allowing students to progress both academically and emotionally. Using this digital resource, student dancers can find balance between their minds and emotions, which helps improve their health and how they perform.

IV. Actual Output:

Powtoon Animation Link: https://youtu.be/fyQv3g45eEw?si=b_rux_HuEMJXEPnX

Part I. Preventive Strategies for Student Dancers

GOAL	PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES	PROCEDURE
Manage time effectively	Priority Planner Challenge	<p>Can be done at home and school:</p> <p>Use sticky notes in different colors available and put the schedule means with date and time (e.g. orange for academic tasks, yellow for the dance schedules, pink for rest breaks, and blue for other personal tasks). This can be put or stick to in a designated notebook for planner, or it can be in a wall or desk area at home where you can see it and be reminded from it. Arrange them by priority to effectively see what is needed to be done first.</p> <p>The suggested activity is recommended to be done at all times.</p>
Improve focus, and release mental health	Study and Stretch	<p>At home:</p> <p>Once done with all the academic activities, assignments, projects to be submitted within the day or a week, and preparing for exams, dedicate and allot 5-10 minutes doing yoga poses for stress relief. However, if time is limited, the researchers do recommend these three known poses on relieving stress: Childs Pose, Easy Pose, and Eagle Pose. But if 5-10 minutes are possible, the researchers recommend to look for "Yoga Poses for Stress Relief" where</p>

		<p>you can follow images posted on websites and can also follow along with youtube videos.</p> <p>The suggested strategy can be done everyday, two days per week, or per week, depending on how student dancers feel</p>
Process emotions and clear mental space	Mind Dump Journaling	At the end of each day, write down all the worries, all the words needed to be released, just everything on your mind. It can include worries about grades, dance pressure or anything else, additionally, not mandatory, put a sentence/s below the words released stating why it leads to all of this.

Part II. Preventive Strategies for Dance Coach

GOAL	PREVENTIVE STRATEGIES	PROCEDURE
Support Student Dancers academically	Focus Flow Warm-Up	<p>The dance coach make the student dancers form into a circle where student dancers have 2-minutes to share how many activities left needed to be accomplished: "5 activities left", "3 more activities", "no activities left". After a student dancers states that, it goes to other student dancers next, just moving quickly from one to next.</p> <p>The suggested preventive strategy can be done 2 times a week.</p>
Foster a mindful break for academic clarity	Academic Pulse Check	<p>Before starting the rehearsals, the dance coach will allocate 5 minutes and will lead the activity. The student dancers must have paper, and it is not recommended to use new paper. Then a pencil, or color, or pen, or anything that can be used for scribbling, and they can sit wherever they are comfortable. The dance coach will play a calming frequency music which can be seen and heard in youtube. While the music is playing, the student dancers will be advised to close their eyes while listening and can start scribbling in their paper, while thinking and releasing their academic pressure or mental load.</p> <p>The suggested strategy can be done 2 or 3 times per month.</p>
Recognize Achievements Holistically	Success Shoutouts	The dance coach will give a shoutout or a simple congratulations whenever a student dancers achieved or accomplished something in front of the team it can be about academics, personal, or dance-related.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Throughout the study, ethical procedures were strictly followed. Before the commencement of data collection, the researchers secured institutional approval of the

institutions and obtained informed consent from all the participants. The respondents' confidentiality, voluntary participation were assured and with the adherence to the data privacy regulations. All ethical guidelines were observed, no part of the study disclosed participants to harm.

REFERENCES

- Ballas, G. (2023.). Academic stress in dancers. Knight Krier. Retrieved from <https://knightkrier.com/8617/features/academic-stress-in-dancers/>
- Bernal, H. L., Jr, Gumaru, R. C. R., & Go, B. B. (2024). Academic Pressure and health habit Formation among Scholars: Basis for Community Health Teaching. *Randwick International of Education and Linguistics Science Journal*, 5(4), 1423–1429. doi: 10.47175/rielsj.v5i4.1107
- Blevins, P., Erskine, S., Hopper, L., & Moyle, G. (2019). Finding Your Balance: An Investigation of Recovery–Stress Balance in Vocational Dance Training. *Journal of Dance Education*, 20(1), 12–22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15290824.2018.153257>
- Brunner, S. (2024). The psychological impacts of competitive dance on young dancers. *Journal of Dance Psychology*, 32(2), 45-58.
- Commission on Higher Education. (2021). Policies, standards, and guidelines on the implementation of tertiary physical education: Physical activity towards health and fitness (PATHFIT) courses (CHED Memorandum Order No. 39, s. 2021). Commission on Higher Education, Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from <https://mimaropa.ched.gov.ph/ched-memorandum-order-no-39-series-of-2021/>
- Daychak, A. (2025). Pros & cons of social media for dancers. *Performing Dance Arts*. Retrieved from <https://www.performingdancearts.ca/pros-cons-social-media-dancers/>
- Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/DO_s2019_021.pdf
- Luga IA, David OA, Danet M. Student Burnout in Children and Adolescents: The Role of Attachment and Emotion Regulation. *Children (Basel)*. 2023 Aug 24;10(9):1443. doi: 10.3390/children10091443. PMID: 37761404; PMCID: PMC10527975.
- Jowett, S., & Cockerill, I. M. (2018). The role of social support in the well-being of dancers. *Journal of Dance Medicine & Science*, 22(4), 157-165. <https://doi.org/10.12678/1089-313X.22.4.157>
- Lopez, Benjamin, "Dance students at a two-year college: Making sense of their academic, cultural, and social world" (2017). *Electronic Theses and Dissertations*. 5384. Retrieved from <https://stars.library.ucf.edu/etd/5384>
- Morozov, E. M., & Sadokha, E. I. (2023). Psychological nature of burnout phenomenon. *Psychological-Pedagogical Journal GAUDEAMUS*, 1, 9–17. <https://doi.org/10.20310/1810-231x-2023-22-1-9-17>
- Olson, N., Oberhoffer-Fritz, R., Reiner, B., & Schulz, T. (2025). Stress, student burnout and study engagement – a cross-sectional comparison of university students of different academic subjects. *BMC Psychology*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-025-02602-6>
- Ramirez, M. L., & Jakaub, V. (2021). Understanding the relationship between academic burnout and field practicum satisfaction (Master's thesis, California State University, San Bernardino). *Electronic Theses, Projects, and Dissertations*, 1259. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/etd/12>

- Rahmati, Z. (2015). The study of academic burnout in students with high and low level of self-efficacy. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 185, 276–280.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.01.087>
- Reynolds, C. (2024, December 27). How mental health can affect dancers' performance. *EW Motion Therapy*. Retrieved April 10, 2025, from
<https://www.ewmotiontherapy.com/blog/mental-health-affect-dancers-performance>
- Saqib, N. U., Raheem, M. A., Iqbal, M., Salman, M., & Shahzad, T. (2018). *Effects of Extracurricular Activities on Students*. National University of Sciences and Technology. Retrieved from
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/327052180_Effects_of_Extracurricular_Activities_on_Students
- Smith, L., Louw, Q. A., & Brink, Y. (2024). Fatigue and recovery in ballet: Exploring the experiences of professional South African ballet dancers. *BMC Sports Science Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 16(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13102-024-01026-w>
- Spinner, J. (2022, July 28). Dancers: Not All Effort is Good Effort. *The Whole Dancer*. Retrieved from <https://www.thewholedancer.com/all-effort-dance/>
- Taylor, J. (2015). *Burn-Out in Dance: Causes and Relief* - Dr. Jim Taylor. Dr. Jim Taylor. Retrieved from <https://www.drjimtaylor.com/4.0/burn-out-in-dance-causes-and-relief/>
- Thomas, F. B. (2022). The role of purposive sampling technique as a tool for informal choices in social sciences in research methods. *Just Agriculture Multidisciplinary E-Newsletter*, 2(5), 1–8. Retrieved from
<https://justagriculture.in/files/newsletter/2022/january/47.%20The%20Role%20of%20Purposive%20Sampling%20Technique%20as%20a%20Tool%20for%20Informal%20Choices%20in%20a%20Social%20Sciences%20in%20Research%20Methods.pdf>
- Tuomilehto, H., Vuorinen, V., Penttilä, E., Kivimäki, M., Vuorenmaa, M., Venojärvi, M., Airaksinen, O., & Pihlajamäki, J. (2016). Sleep of professional athletes: Underexploited potential to improve health and performance. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 35(7), 704–710. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02640414.2016.1184300>
- Tununu AF, Martin P. Prevalence of burnout among nurses working at a psychiatric hospital in the Western Cape. *Curationis*. 2020 Aug 4;43(1):e1-e7.
 Doi:10.4102/curationis.v43i1.2117. PMID: 32787430; PMCID: PMC7479374